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PARTICIPANTS' PERCEPTION OF A FLEXIBLE PEDAGOGICAL QUALIFICATION PROGRAM AT A GERMAN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE COVID-19-YEAR 2020

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The covid-19-pandemic affected pedagogical qualification of academics. It required a sudden digital transformation and reaction on needs for qualification in digital teaching and learning. This study spotlights participants' perceptions on a flexible, needs oriented, hands-on pedagogical qualification program at a German University of Technology in the Covid-19-year 2020. It is questioned how participants evaluated the program. Based on a mixed-method approach, data was gathered using an online survey (8 responses) and semi-structured interviews (4 interviewees). First, the results show that overall the program has been appraised positively and individually diverse regarding program reaction and learning as well as future teaching behavior. Second, participants highlighted most but not all program elements as being beneficial and appropriately transferred into a digital format. Third, participants appraise most program characteristics as appropriately implemented, especially the flexibility. Most participants find an individual compilation of their program more important than running through it in cohort while appreciating, but missing networking opportunities in the digital program version. Fourth, participants needed to develop applicable digital teaching competencies in tools, course design and tackling challenges while these desires have been covered only partly by the program. Finally, participants requested to improve the programs' digital communication and collaboration platform, to strengthen digital teaching and learning in the program and to offer voluntary, foremost informal networking options. Finally, it is argued that a future pedagogical program has to increase digital competence development and requires to be open, agile and multidimensionally supported in order to react to abrupt need changes.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19-pandemic disrupted teaching and learning in higher education, and in turn pedagogical qualification of academics around the world (see [1]). It forced a sudden shift towards comprehensive digital pedagogical trainings (see [2]) and an unprecedented reaction on needs for digital teaching and learning qualification (see e.g. [3]). Complex cohort-like as well as individual pedagogical programs have been evaluated positively prior to the Covid-19 pandemic (see e.g. [4], [5]). Now, this small study spotlights participants' perceptions on a flexible, needs oriented, hands-on pedagogical qualification program at a German University of Technology in the Covid-19-year 2020. It is questioned how participants appraised the program after finalization by the end of 2020. Therefore, this short paper emphasizes participants' reaction, learning and behavior, their view on an individual program compilation, their perception of how their needs in digital teaching and learning were addressed as well as their recommendations for the program development. It concludes on how to handle such a pedagogical qualification program in striving for high quality in ongoing, compelled digital teaching.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Running a pedagogical program

To ensure high quality education, the Executive Committee of a German University of Technology initiated an obligatory pedagogical qualification program, called I³ProTeachING, (see [6]) for research assistants and commissioned its center for teaching and learning (CLL) in cooperation with the graduate academy to implement it. An internationally wide-used framework for researcher development as well as a modified framework for the German context with their teaching lenses/ clusters are used as underlying anchor points (see [7], [8]). This program aims to increase pedagogical competencies in 60 hours within max. two years. It comprises two competence lines, i.e. "Higher Education & Engineering Pedagogy" (HE/EP) (see [9]) and "Research-Based Learning" (RBL) (see [10]) while integrating digital teaching and learning as a cross-cutting topic. It consists of an initial conversation between experts from the CLL and the individual participants, workshops, a personal reflection on teaching, peer visits in courses, projects on teaching innovations, classroom action research or sharing about teaching, a final event with a product presentation and makes use of an e-portfolio. Participants compile their program according their interests and needs in terms of time and content in all program elements within the general program structure. Flexibility, individual pathways and teaching practice are key aspects in the program design and are well located in the manifold teaching activities (see [11]). The program realization started in presence by the end of 2019 and was transformed to digital formats by April 2020 (see [5]).

2.2 Evaluating the pedagogical program

To evaluate the program, we focussed on participants' perception after finalizing their qualification by the end of the year 2020. It was questioned how participants

react to the program, appraise their learning and assess their future teaching intentions. Furthermore, it was of interest how they view the individual program compilation and how their needs in digital teaching and learning qualifications were addressed. Finally, it was asked for recommendations for the program development. The evaluation was designed according to the first three levels of evaluating training programs by Kirckpatrick and Kirckpatrick (2015) ([12]): Reaction (R), learning (L) and behaviour (B). After finalizing the program, a self-designed online survey (n=8 respondents of 13 program graduates, November 2020) and four semi-structured interviews, with interviewees representing various aspects, were conducted (with 2 HE/EP and 2 RBL participants). Descriptive statistical analyses were conducted with the survey data. The interview transcripts were coded using the categories “reaction”, “learning”, “behavior”, “individual & cohort compilation”, “digital teaching competencies needed & addressed”, “digital program realization”, “recommendations”. Based in the codes, we analyzed the interviews using qualitative content analysis.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Participants’ overall reaction, learning and behavior regarding the program

The results of the survey and of the interviews show that overall the program has been appraised positively. First, selected survey results indicate very positive participants’ reaction, learning and behavior (see table 1).

Table 1: Selected results of the program evaluation

Level	#	Item	Ø	n
Reaction	1	I find a structured pedagogical qualification as a research assistant important.	1,0	8
	2	I find it personally valuable that I have participated in the program.	1,5	8
Learning	3	I can develop initial approaches for an aligned course.	1,1	8
	4	I can develop initial approaches for a research-based learning course.	1,3	6
	5	I can develop initial approaches for a digital course.	1,4	8
Behavior	6	I am motivated to develop my own teaching continuously.	1,0	8
	7	I am interested in qualification in higher education pedagogy in the future.	1,3	8

With 3 levels (Reaction, Learning, Behaviour), answers possible on a 4-point scale with 1...totally agree and 4...totally disagree (so lower values show higher agreement), Ø: arithmetic mean; n: number of responses with 2 respondents of the competence line “Higher Education & Engineering Pedagogy” and 6 respondents of the competence line “Research-Based Learning”

Second, the interviews shed light on some dominant positive anticipations, e.g. networking to peers, workshop topics and identification with the competence lines. Furthermore, the interviewees explained to have gained competencies e.g. in terms of designing courses using digital tools and concepts, applying communication methods and developing a self-reflected teaching and research personality. Finally, it is interesting, that they reported on a broad range of teaching intentions like using material on course planning, developing digital courses, engaging in teaching publications and teaching promotion.

3.2 Participants' assessment of the digital program realization

Survey respondents perceived the digital program realization in Covid-19-times as appropriate. They highlighted most program elements as being beneficial (from more to less beneficial: competence line, supervision, workshops, teaching project, peer visit, reflection) besides Mahara (used as e-portfolio, communication and cooperation platform), which was evaluated as not helpful. Furthermore, they valued the realization of the key program characteristics of individual compilation, time and content flexibility as positive. However, needs-orientation and focus on teaching practice was evaluated as moderate only. Interviewees highlighted: The transition from presence to digital workshops was associated with a lack of informal exchange, networking and room to build up a positive group identity.

3.3 Participants' perception on individuality and cohort aspects within the program

Most, but not all survey respondents perceived the individual compilation of the program as more important than running through it as a cohort. In the survey, individual compilation turned out to be an enabling factor for balancing research and teaching duties with fixed or intense timetables and for following individual needs and interests. Three interviewees mentioned less time pressure, the opportunity to look beyond the horizon or into advanced topics as positive when compiling the program individually. Those three assessed more networking as nice to have, but either need to be supported by supervisors or arranged in additional voluntary formats or focussed on innovating teaching practice. Additionally, the third interviewee strongly argued on (potentially) negative group identity dynamics in case that participants reject an obligatory qualification. On the contrary, the fourth interviewee stressed on questioning the individual need coverage: This interviewee valued cohort-like, stable, powerful networking on personal issues and teaching much more important than individual flexibility. This was pointed out to be effective, but making lonely and going beyond an open university-wide discourse and tackling challenges collectively.

3.4 Meeting participants' needs in digital teaching and learning

Survey respondents found it important to achieve applicable digital teaching competencies in tools, course design and tackling challenges in teaching practice. They highlighted that these needs have been covered only partly by the program: Basic digital teaching has been addressed as a topic (e.g. good teaching principles in Zoom, applying flipped classroom concepts), but advanced topics and an overall digital approach did not become obvious in the program. The interviewees illustrated this program shortage regarding quick need-orientation for teaching practice: Interviewees struggled with the cumbersome dialog in front of the black wall in Zoom, they just started with the learning management platform ILIAS, they needed to practice teaching with Zoom, they lacked alternative digital course design and they desired to announce multiple communication channels. One interviewee clarified that

each institute explored manifold digital tools in the beginning before the university made decisions for the main licenced tools to be used.

3.5 Participants' recommendations for program development

To improve the program, participants strongly requested to revise using Mahara. They recommended to strengthen digital teaching and learning in the program regarding advanced topics such as tool variation, exchanging tackling digital teaching challenges, analyzing good practices of digital courses, discussing actual digital implementations concretely and evaluating digital courses. Finally, they proposed to offer various informal networking options, partly attached to a workshop, in order to jointly work on designing digital courses, discussing how to solve hurdles in digital teaching and joyable team building.

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This study highlights the case of a pedagogical qualification program which was conducted in abrupt digital transformation times due to the Covid-19 pandemic. For evaluating the program, two data sets have been used in a common procedure. It should be strongly highlighted that the meaning of the results presented here needs cautious interpretation and is not conclusive due to relative low response numbers in questionnaires and low number of interviews in the shade of the recent global challenge. Based on the results presented here, we conclude that the program was mostly positively evaluated by the participants who responded. It was uncovered that these participants appraised manifold pedagogical learning which however have not been appraised as sufficient when facing the hasty change to digital teaching and learning connected with partly resisting and overwhelming challenges. These participants proposed revisions, which have already been implemented (e.g. focus on digital teaching in the workshop catalog, various formal & informal networking formats) or are under construction (e.g. replacing Mahara by ILIAS). However, it should be strongly argued that, a qualification program is limited (see [13]) and only one opportunity among others to overcome diverse barriers in current digital teaching. In striving for high quality in recently compelled digital teaching, it is synthesized: This pedagogical program needs individual pathways with combined networking options and practice-oriented, comprehensive digital competence development. Further data as well as discussions are desired to revise this program for its recent digital implementation and beyond in the future.

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